

Error Analysis of Written Compositions of Dyslexic Learners in Selected Secondary Schools in Southeast Nigeria

By

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Abstract

Dyslexia is a language-related disorder that has a neurobiological origin. It manifests as reading and spelling disabilities that affect the victims' performance in the target language. This study examines the written texts produced by four dyslexic learners in secondary schools in Anambra and Enugu states, Nigeria, to discover the types and causes of errors in them. Qualitative analysis method is used to examine the data through the lens of Velluntino et al. (2004) Phonological Deficit Theory, whereby the theory's phonological awareness, letter-sound decoding, and word identification components provide the framework for data analysis. Findings reveal the presence of different types of errors, such as orthographic, lexico-semantic, global, and morpho-semantic errors. It is further discovered that the first three types of errors are caused by deficiency in phonological awareness skills, poor knowledge of the language letter-sound decoding system, and word identification challenges. The study concludes that phonological deficiency is a major underlying cause of reading and spelling challenges faced by the dyslexics.

Keywords: Dyslexia, Error analysis, Phonological deficit theory, Phonological awareness

Introduction

Dyslexia is a neurological disorder that manifests as difficulty with developing reading and spelling skills. The reading and spelling challenge is caused by the structural differences in the brain makeup of the victims, which, according to Bhawani et al. (2023), makes them unique. The dyslexics are usually considered as being cognitively impaired. However, studies have shown that though they face challenges with processing and creating written information, they are intelligent and have no challenges using other language mediums. This means that dyslexia is not a cognitive disorder but a neurodevelopmental issue. Nevertheless, it may affect cognitive processes that require extracting information and knowledge from written texts. This is why it is necessary to help dyslexic learners develop reading and spelling skills immediately the problem is diagnosed.

As explained by scholars, such as Lama (2019) and Nijakowska (2015), dyslexics need extensive literacy skills coaching to be able to overcome the challenges surrounding their language skills development they (the learners) cannot develop those skills without assistance. But for a dyslexic learner to be assisted, the coach needs to identify their specific challenges and, therefore, personalise their learning experience. It was discovered that, generally, the major challenges of the dyslexics are caused by their phonological awareness disability, which hinders their ability to identify and represent phonemes with letters. As a result, they commit errors when reading and in spelling. The aim of this study is to examine the errors made by dyslexic learners in selected schools in Southeast Nigeria. Its objectives are to identify the types of errors they commonly commit in their writings and the underlying causes of the errors. This way, the study is able to expose how these errors can be resolved while coaching the affected learners.

Error and Error Analysis

Several researchers have examined errors in the use of language by non-native speakers by identifying their types and causes. Among them are Surdarkan and Erniwati (2022), who examined the errors in the written text of learners of English as a foreign language in Tadulako University. Their research identified five types of errors, which are punctuation (omitted or wrongly added punctuation mark), orthographic (spelling errors), lexico-semantic (wrong word selection), morpho-syntactic (errors in pluralisation, concord, tense, articles, modals, word order, and sentence structure), and capitalisation (wrong capitalisation of words) errors. These errors were discovered to result from lack of knowledge of the English language structures and the interference of the learner's first language. Khansir (2012) agrees that errors in linguistics also include deviations in a target language, which emanates from the interference of the learner's first or second language. Scholars, such as Zhu (2019), Al-Kresheh (2016), and Maruti (2023), nevertheless, argue that committing errors while using a target language is an essential part of its learning process because such errors give an insight into the learner's knowledge of the specific language. In other words, even though errors are expected during language learning process, they should be studied to identify the learners' progress and the areas the instructors should work on.

Muqbel (2018) explains that the act of studying, identifying, describing, and explaining errors are all known as error analysis. He further observes that second and foreign language learners can make errors in their use of the target language as a result of partial or faulty learning of the language in question. His study further identified four types of errors in the texts of second language learners. These are omission (absence of a syntactic or morphological components that prevents proper interpretation), addition (inclusion of incorrect or unnecessary item in a sentence), misformation (using wrong form of grammatical element), and misordering (wrong positioning of words in sentences or morphemes in words) errors. Yilmaz and Demir (2020), however, observe that the errors committed by these learners can be categorised into linguistic errors (orthographic, phonological, lexico-semantic, morphological, and syntactic errors), cognitive processing errors (omission, addition, substitution, and permutation), communicative (local and global errors), punctuation, and spelling errors.

The reviewed studies view errors as the outcome of poor knowledge of the target language. As a result, none of them examined errors in written composition of dyslexic learners. It is also observed that none of them examined the errors through the perspective of Velluntino et al. (2004) Phonological Deficit Theory. This study, however, focuses on the errors found in written compositions of learners with dyslexia, which are analysed through the lens of Velluntino et al. (2004) Phonological Deficit Theory in order to identify the type of errors they commit and their underlying causes.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts Velluntino et al. (2004) Phonological Deficit Theory as its theoretical anchor. This theory posits that many dyslexics encounter phonological awareness deficiency in their respective languages and that causes them to encounter difficulties while attempting to identify, represent, process, store, and retrieve distinct speech sounds. The inability of the dyslexics to perform the aforementioned further causes their difficulty with building larger linguistic units, such as words, phrases, clauses, and sentences, with the sounds in their language. Put differently, the phonological awareness deficit encountered by the dyslexics prevents them from developing the ability to use the sounds in their language to create words and other linguistic units.

The Phonological Deficit Theory contains seven components or tenets, which provides different frameworks for diagnosing phonological awareness deficits in the victims of dyslexia. These components are phonological awareness (tests language users' ability to identify and accurately process sound elements in words), word identification (tests the ability to recognise words in texts), letter-sound decoding (tests the ability to identify the sound an alphabet represents), and confrontational naming (tests the ability to identify objects and retrieve their names from memory). Others are rapid naming (tests the ability to quickly identify and accurately name items in series), verbal learning (tests the ability to learn and recall words), and verbal memory (tests the ability to retrieve verbal information from memory). Nevertheless, this study utilises only three of these components, which are phonological awareness, word identification, and letter-sound decoding. The phonological awareness, word identification, and letter-sound decoding components provide the framework for identifying, categorising, and describing the errors in the study samples. With that, the study is able to identify the specific spelling challenges the learners face.

Methodology

Data for this study were collected from the composition written by four dyslexic learners, between the ages of 12 and 14, who were in two junior secondary schools in Awka, Anambra State, and Enugu, Enugu State, both in Southeast geopolitical zone, Nigeria. The learners were purposively selected from seven reportedly dyslexic learners. The researchers collaborated with the school managements and teachers to identify dyslexic learners. Four learners from Awka and three from Enugu were selected by the teachers as the suspected dyslexic learners. However, after the first interaction with the students, it was discovered that one of them had hearing and speaking impairments, while two recently moved to the urban area from rural communities, where they were not well drilled in literacy skills development. These three participants were removed from the study. As a result, the remaining participants were two each from Awka and Enugu.

The participants were given two different writing tasks to complete. In the first one, they were provided with ten words extracted from Middle Basic 1 and 2 (Primary 4 and 5) English textbooks and instructed to make sentences with them. This task enabled the observation of the learners' ability to identify words as well as evaluate their letter-sound decoding and phonological awareness skills. The second task required the participants to write a brief essay about their towns. This task also allows the researchers to observe their letter-sound decoding and phonological awareness abilities. The errors found in the written tasks of the participants formed the data for this study. They were qualitatively analysed through the lens of Velluntino et al. (2004) Phonological Deficit Theory. The three utilised tenets of the theory formed the theoretical framework for identifying, categorising, and describing the errors.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The analysis of data is segmented into two to capture the two tasks given to the learners. The first section presents and analyses the data from sentence making task while the second section focuses on data from short composition on the topic, "Your Town". The three components of the Phonological Deficit Theory – word identification, phonological awareness, and letter-sound decoding – are used to examine the performance of the learners in order to identify the type and causes of their errors. Furthermore, the participants are labelled with the alphabetic letters – A (female, 14 years old, JS 2), B (male, 15 years old, JS 2), C (male, 12 years old, JS 2), and D (male, 13 years old, JS 1) – to grant them anonymity.

Sentence-Making Task

This component tests the learners' ability to identify and read ten words provided to them for sentence making task. Table 1 is a breakdown of the learners' performance in the task.

Table 1: Errors in the Sentence-Making Task

Data Presentation			Data Analysis	
Word	Learner	Sentence	Error Type	Description
Man	A	He is a man.	No errors	N/A
	B	My father is a rich man	No errors	N/A
	C	That man is my father.	No errors	N/A
	D	I am a man.	No errors	N/A
Boat	A	I am in the boat	No errors	N/A
	B	Mr Okoro have a boat.	Morpho-syntactic	Use of "have" instead of "has"
	C	The Boat is leaving	Capitalisation	"boat" is a common noun
	D	a sci a Boat	Orthographic (a, sci), capitalisation (boat)	"I see" is spelt as "a sci"; "boat" is a common noun

Break	A	I am Breaking wood	Capitalisation	“breaking” is a verb
	B	I will break that toy	No errors	N/A
	C	Break the stick and give me one	No errors	N/A
	D	I have Break	Capitalisation (break), morpho-syntactic (omission of the article “a”)	“break” is an abstract noun in this context
Phone	A	I have a phone.	No errors	N/A
	B	The phone is ringing	No errors	N/A
	C	My phone is at Home	Capitalisation	“home” is a common noun
	D	-	N/R (no response)	N/A
Eat	A	I am eating.	No errors	N/A
	B	I Eat rice and beans yearstday	Capitalisation (eat), orthographic (yearstday), morpho-syntactic (“eat”)	“eat” is a verb and should be in the past tense; “yesterday” is wrongly spelt
	C	It is time to Eat luach	Capitalisation, orthographic	“eat” is a verb and is wrongly capitalised; “lunch” is spelt wrongly
	D	I have a Eat	Capitalisation, lexico-semantic	“eat” is a verb and should not be the object of the sentence
Carry	A	I am carry a boket	Morpho-syntactic, orthographic	The present participle “carrying” should be used; “bucket” is spelt wrongly
	B	I can help you to carry the books	Syntactic	The preposition “to” is unnecessarily added
	C	Carry the Baby he is cring	Punctuation, capitalisation, orthographic	Omission of a semicolon after “baby”; “baby” is a common noun and should not be capitalised; “crying” is wrongly spelt
	D	-	N/R	N/A
Fight	A	They are fighting	No errors	N/A
	B	I am going to fight with you	No errors	N/A
	C	They fight always	No errors	N/A

	D	-	N/R	N/A
Sheep	A	I am in the sheep	Lexico-Semantic	Unless used figuratively, humans cannot be inside a sheep
	B	The sheep is hungary	Orthographic	“hungry” is wrongly spelt
	C	The sheep is a male	Morpho-syntactic	Unnecessary addition of the article “a”
	D	I have sheep	Morpho-Syntactic	Omission of a quantifier to indicate if the noun is singular or plural
Cost	A	This cloth cost 5000	No errors	N/A
	B	You are the cost of my problem	Lexico-semantic	Wrong use of the word “cost”
	C	The cost is clear	Lexico-semantic	Wrong use of the word “cost”
	D	I have sci a pesci the cost	Global	The structure, orthography, and word choice prevent comprehension
Cut	A	I am cuting a Bread	Orthographic, morpho-syntactic, capitalisation	“cutting” is wrongly spelt; “bread” is capitalised even though it is not a proper noun
	B	I will cut that cloth into pices	Orthographic	“pieces” is wrongly spelt
	C	I cut my hand with knife	No errors	N/A
	D	I have cut ssowon	Orthographic	“someone” is wrongly spelt

On table 1, errors are not identified in the sentences made with “man” and a few other cases, such as where Learners A and B make sentences with “break”, “phone”, and “fight”. Learner D also fails to attempt constructing sentences with “phone”, “carry”, and “fight” for unverified reasons. Different types of errors are, however, identified in the sentences constructed with other provided words. The table also reveals that the learners fail to punctuate their sentences correctly. This is more prominent in their failures to add full stops at the end of their declarative sentences.

Short Composition Task

Some of the errors found in the composition written by the learners are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Errors in the Short Composition Task (My Town)

Data Presentation		Data Analysis	
Learner	Expression	Error Type	Description
A	It is a Big town	Capitalisation	“big” is an adjective
	When we get they we see our family relations	Lexico-semantic, punctuation, global	“they” is used instead of “there”; there is no comma after “they/there”; it is unclear if the action is in the past or future
	We Normaly stay 2 weeks	Capitalisation, orthographic	“normally” is wrongly spelt and also capitalised even though it is an adverb
	We live in christain town	Capitalisation, morpho-syntactic orthographic	“Christian” is wrongly spelt and it is not capitalised; an article is omitted
	Why i love my village is that it is pace, friendly and kind	Capitalisation, lexico-semantic	The personal pronoun “I” is not capitalised; “pace” is wrongly used in the sentence
B	In our marketday you can see many stof such Tomatos, cloth, pepper and so on and sofor	Orthographic, morpho-syntactic, capitalisation	“market day”, “stuffs”, “tomatoes”, and “so forth” are wrongly spelt; “stuff” is not pluralised; “tomatoes” is capitalised
	In my village our new yam fastever in Agust	Orthographic, punctuation	“festival” and “August” are spelt wrongly; comma is omitted after village
	In my village we have rever called kalawa	Punctuation, orthographic, capitalisation	Comma is omitted after village; “river” is wrongly spelt; the name of the river should be capitalised
	Our maskrat time is in Agust	Orthographic	“masquerade” and “August” are wrongly spelt
	My village is the most purpula village in Enugu state	Orthographic, capitalisation	“popular” is wrongly spelt; “state” should be capitalised

C	the citie is good and Brafi citie because they have searuret and other thing	Global	“citie” and “becouse” are wrongly spelt; it is difficult to decode the words “Brafi” and “searuret”; “thing” should be pluralised
	one thing that make me to like the citie is that they are hard Working and they are a good farms	Syntactic, orthographic, capitalisation, lexico-semantic, morpho-syntactic, global	Sentence is not started with a capital letter; the preposition, “to”, is added after “make”; “city” is wrongly spelt; “make” should have the –s suffix; “working is capitalised”; “a” and “farms” make the last part of the expression difficult to comprehend
	they love one and other	Capitalisation, Lexico-semantic	Sentence is not started with a capital letter; “another” is replaced with “and other”
	they bo thing together	Capitalisation, Orthographic; morpho-syntactic	The sentence is not started with a capital letter; “do” is spelt as “bo”
	Thing you for read it	Lexico-semantic, morpho-syntactic	“thank” is wrongly replaced with “thing”; “reading” is written as “read”
D*	I have Go to the tcis that I sso the	Global	The structure and words make comprehension impossible

D* - the learner constructed only this sentence in the short composition task.

Table 2 shows the different errors found in the short composition the learners wrote about their town. However, Learner D faced challenges with drafting the short composition and could not write more than the erroneous sentence presented in the table.

Discussion of Findings

The objectives this study focus on discovering the types of errors in the written texts of dyslexic learners in secondary schools and the possible causes of the errors. The study hence reveals that the dyslexics make different kinds of errors, especially capitalisation, punctuation, morphosyntactic, orthographic, lexico-semantic, and global errors. The capitalisation errors are seen in situations, where they fail to begin

sentences with capital letters as well as where they inappropriately capitalised common nouns in sentences. The major cases of punctuation errors are found where they fail to close sentences with a full stop while the morphosyntactic errors are commonly committed in cases of concord and tense errors. These three errors (capitalisation, punctuation, and morphosyntactic errors) are not further discussed in this section because they fall beyond the scope of Vellutino et al. (2004) Phonological Deficit Theory, which forms the theoretical framework for the study. Hence, the remaining three errors (orthographic, lexico-semantic, and global errors) are discussed in details because they fall within the scope of Phonological Deficit Theory and also capture how deficiency in the language phonological aspects causes errors in the performance of the captured learners. They are errors that result from the learners' deficiency in phonological awareness, letter-sound decoding, and word identification skills.

In Table 1, the learners exhibit their phonological awareness deficiency by misspelling "yesterday" (spelt as "yearstday"), "lunch" (spelt as "luach"), "someone" (spelt as "ssowon"), and "hungry" (spelt as "hungary"). These orthographic errors reveal that the learners spelt the words the way they pronounced them. They reveal the learners' inability to identify the sounds in the words. Furthermore, misspelling words, such as "see" (spelt as "sci"), "bucket" (spelt as "boket), "pieces" (spelt as "pices"), "crying" (spelt as "cring"), and "cutting" (spelt as "cuting"), as presented in Table 1 reveal letter-sound decoding deficiency in the learners because the errors show that the learners are aware of phonological components of the words but lack knowledge of how they are orthographically represented. Other instances of letter-sound decoding deficiency are contained in table 2, where "normally", "stuff", "so forth", "city", "festival", "August", and "river" are wrongly spelt as *normaly*, *stof*, *sofot*, *citie*, *fastever*, *Agust*, and *rever*, respectively. Phonological awareness deficiency is also found in Table 2, where "masquerade" is spelt as *maskrat* and "do" spelt as *bo*.

Instances of word identification challenges are identified in the lexico-semantic and global errors found in the learners' performances. In Table 1, for example, the following words are used wrongly in sentences: eat (Learner D), sheep (Learner A), and cost (Learners B, C, & D). Table 2 further captures the wrong use of they (Learner A), pace (Learner A), farms (Learner C), and thing (Learner D). Some instances of global errors, especially as committed by Learner D (Table 1 – cost, and Table 2), reveal that the learner could not identify the words used in sentences.

Conclusion

Young dyslexic learners face reading and spelling difficulties, which hinder their performance in their target language. This study has identified some of the major errors they commit in their writing as caused by challenges with recognising certain words (word identification), difficulties with discerning the right letters to represent sounds with (letter-sound decoding), and little or no knowledge of the sounds contained in certain words (phonological awareness). These errors further indicate that one of the major reasons dyslexic learners encounter reading and spelling challenges is phonological deficit or deficiency. This means that their neurobiological structure is hindering their ability to identify the sounds in words as well as learn how to represent those sounds orthographically without deviating from the standardised system used for the

language. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that teachers, curriculum developers, and instructional material creators focus on developing educational materials and classroom activities that will help dyslexics improve their phonological skills. Further studies should be conducted to identify the underlying reasons for morpho-syntactic errors in the written texts of dyslexic learners.

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